

INSULTNI O‘TKAZGAN BEMORLARDA TIBBIY REABILITATSIYANI UY SHAROITIDA TASHKIL ETISH VA TAHLIL QILISH

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Tadqiqot maqsadi: insultni o‘tkazgan bemorlarda reabilitatsiyani uy sharoitida olib borish va reabilitatsiya davomiyligiga natijalarning bog‘liqligini o‘rganish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: 2023-2024 yillar oralig‘ida “Reabilitatsiya” markazi a‘zolari Toshkent shahrida 82 nafar insult o‘tkazgan bemorlarga reabilitatsiya yordamini ko‘rsatishdi. Reabilitatsiya yordamiga davolovchi jismoniy mashqlar va fiziodavolash usullari kiritildi. O‘tkazilgan reabilitatsiya samaradorligi maxsus test va shkalalar yordamida baholanib borildi.

Olingan natijalar: Bemorlardagi o‘zgarishlarni baholash uchun biz mushak kuchini baholash shkalasidan, harakat indeksi uchun indeks Berteldan, qo‘llardagi (FAM-UE) va oyoqlardagi (FAM-LE) harakatni maxsus testlar bilan baholab bordik.

Mushak kuchini baholaganda 18 % da “0” ball, 34 % da “1” ball va 48% da “2” ball bilan baholandi. Bu katta qism bemorlarda, mushaklar taranglashgani ammo harakatning yo‘qligini bildiradi.

Indeks Bertelda esa 8% da 0-20 ballgach bo‘lib, to‘liq yordamga muhtoj, 92% bemorlarimiz 25-60 ball bilan baholanib, yaqqol yordamga muhtoj deb baholandi.

Qo‘llardagi (FAM-UE) harakatni maxsus testi 0-20 ball va oyoqlardagi (FAM-LE) harakatni maxsus testi 0-8 ball oralig‘ida, bu kasallarning o‘rtacha natijalari bo‘lib og‘ir harakat buzilishi deb mutaxassislar tomonidan baholandi.

82 nafar bemorlarimiz uchun 9 oylik (N=21, 25,6%), 6 oylik (N=45, 54,9%) va 3 oylik (N=16, 19,5%) reabilitatsiya dasturida ishlab chiqdik, dasturimiz tarkibiga faol va nofaol davolovchi jismoniy mashqlar kiritilib, uning asosiy vazifasi mushaklar tonusini oshirish, trofikani yaxshilash va harakatni tiklashdan iborat bo‘ldi.

Xulosa:

1. Insult asosan keksa yoshli insonlar orasida ko‘proq va aynan ayollar orasida 67%) katta foizni tashkil qiladi.
2. Etiologik omillardan eng ko‘p qismi gipodinamiya va semizlik egallaydi.
3. Bemorlarimizning eng keng tarqalgan shikoyati asosan bir tomonlama gemiparez va gemipligiya bo‘ldi.

References:

1. Allen L., John-Baptiste A., Meyer M., et al. Evaluation of the impact of a home stroke rehabilitation program: a cost-effectiveness study. *Disabil Rehabil* 2019;41:2060–5. [10.1080/09638288.2018.1459879](https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2018.1459879) [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. American Heart Association. *Heart Disease and Stroke Statistics – 2004 Update*. Dallas, Texas: American Heart Association; 2003. [Google Scholar]
3. Bonita R., Mendis S., Truelsen T., et al. Global Stroke Initiative. *Lancet Neurol* 2004;3:391–3. [10.1016/S1474-4422\(04\)00800-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(04)00800-2) [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Brandstater M.E. Review of stroke rehabilitation. *Stroke*. 1990;21:1140–2. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

5. Di Carlo A. Human and economic burden of stroke. *Age Ageing* 2009;38:4–5. 10.1093/ageing/afn282 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Kulkantrakorn K, Jirapramukpitak T. A prospective study of cumulative incidence of depression after ischemic stroke and Parkinson's disease over one year: preliminary study. *J Neurol Sci.* 2007;263:165–8. doi: 10.1016/j.jns.2007.07.014. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Langhorne P, Bernhardt J, Kwakkel G. Stroke rehabilitation. *Lancet* 2011;377:1693–702. 10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60325-5 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Lais D, Enon H, Makovjak-Kordoliani M.A, et al. Post-stroke dementia. *Lancet Neurol* 2005;4:752–9. 10.1016/S1474-4422(05)70221-0 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Robinson-Smith G, Johnston M.V, Allen J. Self-care, self-efficacy, quality of life, and depression after stroke. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* 2000;81:460–4. doi: 10.1053/mr.2000.3863. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Anderson CS, Jamrozik KD, Stewart-Wynne EG. Models of hospital emergency care, rehabilitation, and discharge after acute stroke: the Perth Stroke Study 1989–1990. *Cerebrovasc Dis.* 1994;4:344–53. [Google Scholar]
11. Burvill PW, Johnson GA, Jamrozik KD, et al. Anxiety disorders after stroke: results from the Perth Community Stroke Study. *Br J Psychiatry.* 1995;166:328–32. doi: 10.1192/bjp.166.3.328. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
12. Dam M, Tonin P, Casson S, et al. The impact of long-term rehabilitation therapy on patients with hemiplegia after stroke. *Stroke.* 1993;24:1186–91. doi: 10.1161/01.str.24.8.1186. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
13. Dharmasaroja P. Baseline characteristics of patients with acute ischemic stroke in a suburban area of Thailand. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis.* 2008;17:82–5. doi: 10.1016/j.jstrokecerebrovasdis.2007.11.005. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
14. Dodakian L, McKenzie AL, Le V, et al. A home telerehabilitation program for stroke patients. *Neurorehabil Neural Repair* 2017;31:923–33. 10.1177/1545968317733818 [DOI] [Free PMC Article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
15. Duncan P, Richards L, Wallace D, et al. A randomized controlled pilot study of a home exercise program for individuals with mild to moderate stroke. *Stroke.* 1998;29:2055–60. doi: 10.1161/01.str.29.10.2055. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
16. Duncan PW, Jorgensen HS, Wade DT. Outcomes of acute stroke research: a systematic review and some recommendations for improving practice. *Stroke.* 2000;31:1429–38. doi: 10.1161/01.str.31.6.1429. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
17. Feys HM, De Weerd WJ, Selz BE, et al. The effect of therapeutic intervention for the hemiplegic upper limb in the acute phase after stroke. A simple blind randomized controlled multicenter trial. *Stroke.* 1998;29:785–92. doi: 10.1161/01.str.29.4.785. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
18. Langhorne P, Baylan S, Early Supported Discharge Trialists. Early supported discharge services for people with acute stroke. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2017;7:CD000443. 10.1002/14651858.CD000443.pub4 [DOI] [Free PMC Article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
19. Page SJ, Levine P, Sisto SA, et al. Mental practice combined with physical practice for upper extremity motor deficit in subacute stroke. *Phys Ther.* 2001;81:1455–62. doi: 10.1093/ptj/81.8.1455. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

20. Siemonsma P, Döpp C, Alpay L, et al. Factors influencing the implementation of home rehabilitation after stroke: a systematic review. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2014;36:2019–30. doi: 10.3109/09638288.2014.885091. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
21. Stephens S, Kenny RA, Rowan E, et al. Neuropsychological characteristics of mild vascular cognitive impairment and dementia after stroke. *Int J Geriatr Psychiatry.* 2004;19:1053–7. doi: 10.1002/gps.1209. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

